

**GENETICS AND ENVIRONMENT - THE INFLUENCE OF THE
ENVIRONMENT ON INTELLECT**

Avezov Olmos Ravshanovich¹

Associate Professor of
olmosavezov85@gmail.com

Shavkatova Shakhnoza Pulot qizi²

Student of the Faculty of Pedagogy
shahnozashavkatova20@gmail.com

¹Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

²Bukhara State University

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ANNOTATION

The article provides information about intelligence and factors in its development. Opinions, opinions, studies and their results about the impact of genetics and environment on the development of intelligence are presented. Information about the history of the origin of the tests created for the purpose of measuring intelligence is highlighted.

Key words: Intelligence, genetics, ability, intelligence, mental age, chronological age, mental retardation, mental ability.

Introduction: Intellect (Latin: intellects — knowledge, understanding, perception) — the mental ability of a person, the ability to accurately reflect and change life and the environment in the mind, the ability to think, read and learn, to know the world and to accept social experience; the ability to solve various issues, come to a decision, act rationally, foresee events. Intelligence includes mental processes such as perception, memory, thinking, and speech. The development of intelligence depends on social factors such as innate talent, brain capacity, energetic activity, and life experience. The level of intelligence is determined by the results of human activity, as well as psychological tests.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Imagine if the intellect is inherited from our ancestors, why don't we all think the same, why our abilities and outlook are not exactly the same as our brothers or sisters or even twins? It is this question that has interested people for several thousand years, and most of the research conducted around the world is related to genetic analysis and its results. According to some sources, intellectual abilities are inherited, they are nurtured by the environment and society. Even if we all grew up in the same intellectually stimulating environment, we would have different abilities. The reason is that our experiences also affect the intellect. The use of special tests to assess intelligence began in the late 19th and

early 20th centuries. Initially, intelligence tests were created by A. Binne, who mainly used these tests to determine the IQ of mentally retarded high school students, as well as to recruit soldiers for the military units typical of that time. used in the transfer. The initial task was to assess the level of development of children in order to determine further education programs at school, taking into account individual characteristics. As a measure of the development of intelligence, it was proposed to consider the ratio of the child's actual chronological age and his "mental age". Mental age is determined by performing tasks that children of a certain age can usually solve. The difference between mental and chronological age was considered an indicator of mental retardation (mental age below chronological age) or mental ability (mental age above chronological age). At the same time, the intelligence quotient (IQ) was proposed: $(\text{mental age} / \text{chronological age}) \times 100\%$.

Research results:

A study was conducted to determine the correlation of similarity of intelligence, and the result was as follows. Twins and siblings participated in the experiment. In this case, twins raised together in the same environment, twins raised separately, twins of the same sex and twins of different sexes were raised in the same and different environments. This study found that same-sex twins who were raised in the same environment had similar outcomes compared to twins who were raised in different environments and of the same sex. To date, research has confirmed the importance of both genetics and the environment in the development of intelligence, but there is no evidence based on concrete facts.

Conclusion: Based on the given information and experiences, I can say that circumstances play an important role in the formation of the abilities that each person has. By providing developmental placements that match each child's talents, we can ensure equity and excellence for all.

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